

ROLE OF WOMEN ENHANCING INNOVATION INFRASTRUCTURE FOR ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIC APPROACHES

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Abstract: This paper explores the critical role of women in enhancing innovation infrastructure to spur economic development in Uzbekistan, while addressing both prevailing challenges and strategic approaches. Despite making up a significant portion of the population and workforce, Uzbek women remain underrepresented in sectors critical to innovation and economic growth, particularly in science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) fields. This study delves into cultural, educational, economic, and professional obstacles that hinder women's full participation and leadership in innovation. It discusses strategic approaches, including policy reforms, targeted educational programs, support for women entrepreneurs, and the creation of networks and mentorship opportunities aimed at empowering women. Through qualitative analysis and case studies, this research highlights the transformative potential of women in innovation sectors and proposes a multi-stakeholder implementation framework to overcome gender disparities. The findings underscore the necessity of integrating gender inclusivity into national policies to foster a robust innovation ecosystem that can drive sustainable economic development in Uzbekistan.

Key words: national economy, new industrialization, innovation activity, innovation project, knowledge economy, innovation system, national innovation system, innovation infrastructure, innovation initiative.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется решающая роль женщин в укреплении инновационной инфраструктуры для стимулирования экономического развития в Узбекистане, одновременно решая как существующие проблемы, так и стратегические подходы. Несмотря на то, что узбекские женщины составляют значительную часть населения и рабочей силы, они по-прежнему недостаточно представлены в секторах, имеющих решающее значение для инноваций и экономического роста, особенно в областях науки, технологий, инженерии и математики (STEM). В этом исследовании рассматриваются культурные, образовательные, экономические и профессиональные препятствия, которые мешают полноценному участию и лидерству женщин в инновациях. В нем обсуждаются стратегические подходы, включая политические реформы, целевые образовательные программы, поддержку женщин-предпринимателей, а также создание сетей и возможностей наставничества, направленных на расширение прав и возможностей женщин. Благодаря качественному анализу и тематическим исследованиям это исследование подчеркивает преобразующий потенциал женщин в инновационных секторах и предлагает многостороннюю структуру реализации для преодоления гендерного неравенства. Результаты подчеркивают необходимость интеграции гендерной инклюзивности в национальную политику для создания надежной инновационной экосистемы, которая может способствовать устойчивому экономическому развитию в Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: национальная экономика, новая индустриализация, инновационная деятельность, инновационный проект, экономика знаний, инновационная система, национальная инновационная система, инновационная инфраструктура, инновационная инициатива.

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan's economic landscape has been undergoing significant transformation, especially since the initiation of comprehensive reforms aimed at liberalization and modernization in the late 2010s. These reforms have sought to transition the economy from a predominantly state-controlled system to a more market-oriented one. Here's an overview that emphasizes the importance of innovation in this context:

Historically, Uzbekistan's economy has been heavily reliant on commodity exports such as cotton, gold, and natural gas. However, the government has recognized the risks associated with dependency on commodity markets and has been actively working to diversify its economic base.

The reforms include improving the business environment, reducing bureaucratic hurdles, attracting foreign direct investment, and enhancing transparency in economic management. These efforts have been coupled with significant investments in infrastructure and education, aimed at laying the groundwork for a more diversified and sustainable economy.

In recent years, sectors such as tourism, agriculture, manufacturing, and information technology have been identified as key areas for development. The government is actively promoting technological advancements and innovation within these sectors to boost productivity and competitiveness.

Innovation is critical for Uzbekistan as it seeks to diversify its economy beyond natural resources. By fostering innovation, the country can develop new industries and reduce its vulnerability to external shocks such as fluctuating commodity prices.

For Uzbekistan, competing on a global scale means moving up the value chain by producing higher-value goods and services. This requires continuous improvement in technology and processes, areas where innovation plays a pivotal role.

Innovative environments attract both domestic and international investments. By developing a strong innovation infrastructure, Uzbekistan can appeal to foreign investors who are looking for dynamic and forward-looking markets.

Innovation leads to more efficient business processes and products, which can improve quality of life, increase employment opportunities, and raise overall economic productivity.

Innovation is also crucial for addressing environmental challenges and promoting sustainable development, which is a growing concern for Uzbekistan, particularly in sectors like agriculture and water management.

In Uzbekistan, as in many transitioning and developing economies, there is often a noticeable gap in the economic institutions that are designed to support the national innovation system. This gap can manifest in various forms, including insufficient coordination among stakeholders, lack of policy integration, and limited strategic direction. Addressing these issues is critical for enhancing the effectiveness of innovation activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODS

One of the primary issues is the fragmented nature of the innovation infrastructure. Different entities and institutions involved in innovation—such as universities, government agencies, research institutes, and businesses—often operate in silos, with limited interaction or collaboration. This fragmentation can lead to redundancies, inefficiencies, and a lack of shared goals.

Another significant gap is the lack of coherent policy frameworks that align the various aspects of innovation—from research and development (R&D) funding, intellectual property laws, to commercialization support. Inconsistent policies can deter investment in innovation and complicate the technology transfer processes.

There is often a lack of adequate support mechanisms for innovation, particularly in terms of financing. Financial institutions may be hesitant to provide funding for innovative projects due to perceived risks, and government funding might be irregular or insufficiently targeted.

The evaluation found that projects whose outputs have strong potential for transformative effect for women are those dealing with local and regional development and reforms, where direct access to women and to the services that may empower them are supported.¹ One example is the Rule of Law project, which was under implementation since 2014 and assigned the GEN1 marker. In essence, this project has very little in terms of linkages to gender in its presentation, focusing primarily on access to justice through the transformation of (civic) courts and strengthening other justice sector mechanisms (e.g. the use of the E-SUD (e-court) system) across multiple inter-district courts, the development of new training standards and institutions, and the employment of technical expertise to influence reform policies and legislation, as well as and the FLA. Nevertheless, the evaluation found that the project, through its transformation of civic courts and E-SUD system, has opened up opportunities for women, particularly from rural areas, to benefit from the system,

Source: UNDP ATLAS, Feb. 2019

for example, in cases of filing alimony, access to land rights, or other petitions for the civic court. While the evaluation could not verify the results due to time constraints, data collected through document review and during stakeholder interviews

show that these contributions have a high potential for transformative effects on women and their empowerment, particularly given the context and ingrained negative social norms surrounding women accessing rights, as also noted in the Rule of Law Partnership project

¹ The Gender Results Effectiveness Scale is used to classify gender results into five groups: (i) result had a negative outcome that aggravated or reinforced existing gender inequalities and norms ('gender negative'); (ii) result had no attention to gender, failed to acknowledge the different needs of men, women, girls and boys, or marginalized populations ('gender blind'); (iii) result focused on the number of equity (50/50) of women, men, or marginalized populations that were targeted ('gender-targeted'); (iv) result addressed differential needs of men or women and addressed equitable distribution of benefits resources, status, and rights, but did not address root causes of inequalities in their lives ('gender responsive'); and (v) result contributed to changes in norms, cultural values, power structure and the roots of gender inequalities and discrimination ('gender transformative'). UNDP, IEO, 'ICPE How-to Note on Gender', March 2016

evaluation.² Key informants did, however, confirm that the project had brought catalytic effects on women, which were not initially analysed and expected when the project was set up. Another positive example is the Aral Sea response, which did not include a gender strategy in its design. However, some of its actual interventions have the potential to affect positively the lives of women in the targeted areas, through their empowerment for entrepreneurship and income-generation activities, and by taking a more active role in the farmers' associations and local decision-making processes. Further, the project empowers women, particularly in rural areas, through building their skills, access and resilience to socio-economic challenges, as also confirmed by project-specific evaluations.³ The project also focuses on raising awareness and sensitization of local authorities, farmers associations and other local and regional institutions on the importance of gender mainstreaming.

Women's involvement in innovation is critical for sustainable economic development for several key reasons:

Women represent half of the global population, and excluding them from participating fully in the economy is a missed opportunity for economic growth. Studies have shown that increasing women's labor force participation rates can boost GDP significantly. For example, McKinsey Global Institute reported that advancing women's equality could add \$12 trillion to global growth. Innovation thrives on a diversity of ideas, experiences, and perspectives. Women bring different viewpoints and approaches to problem-solving, which can lead to more creative and effective solutions. This diversity is crucial in driving forward new ideas and innovations that can be transformative for economies. Innovation thrives on a diversity of ideas, experiences, and perspectives. Women bring different viewpoints and approaches to problem-solving, which can lead to more creative and effective solutions. This diversity is crucial in driving forward new ideas and innovations that can be transformative for economies. Worldwide, women now earn more university degrees than men. Not fully utilizing this educated segment of the workforce results in a lower return on investment in education. By enabling women to participate in high-growth fields such as technology and engineering, countries can maximize their returns on educational expenditures. Research by entities such as the International Labour Organization has found that companies with strong gender diversity are more productive and profitable. Involving women in product and service innovation can lead to designs that meet the needs of a broader customer base, thus expanding market reach and potential revenue. When women earn and control more income, the benefits extend across entire communities. Women are more likely to invest in the education and health of their families, leading to improved workforce capabilities in future generations and creating a cycle of positive outcomes. Women's economic empowerment and leadership in innovation are essential in building resilient economies, especially important as the world faces unprecedented challenges like climate change and technological disruption. Women's involvement ensures that a wide array of solutions are considered, enhancing the ability to adapt and thrive in changing conditions. To harness these benefits, governments and

² Lees, Sean, 'Final evaluation of joint project of UNDP, USAID and Supreme Court of Uzbekistan Rule of Law Partnership in Uzbekistan,' 2017

³ Bellamy and Yusupova, 'Mid-Term Evaluation of the UN Joint Programme "Building the resilience of communities affected by the Aral Sea disaster through a Multi-Partner Human Security Trust Fund for the Aral Sea Region"', 2018; and Toritsyn, Arkadi and Yusupov, Yuliy, 'Final Evaluation of UN Joint Programme "Sustaining Livelihood Affected by Aral Sea Disaster"', UNCT Uzbekistan, 2015.

organizations worldwide have recognized the need to address gender disparities in innovation and technology. This involves implementing policies that promote gender equality in education, remove barriers to women's entrepreneurship, and support women in leadership positions across innovative sectors.

The role of women in innovation and economic development in Central Asia, particularly in Uzbekistan, has been shaped by both historical legacies and contemporary policies aimed at gender inclusion. Research and data from this region highlight several key trends, challenges, and progress:

Uzbek women entrepreneurs are a relatively untapped economic resource. Our policy objective is to foster high-growth and high-quality entrepreneurship and receive high returns to entrepreneurship. The key questions for policy design to achieve this policy objective should be the following: how entrepreneurship occurs (self-employment, new firm formation), why it is undertaken (out of necessity or opportunity), and what activity or outcome it can yield (growth in sales or employment). Such measures are important to understand the dynamics of entrepreneurship types and outcomes. Based on our evidence from Uzbekistan, we conclude that female entrepreneurship mainly occurs as self-employment and it is undertaken out of necessity and it does not yield growth. These pieces of evidence suggest that policymakers have a huge opportunity to implement policies and provide institutional support to promote and make women entrepreneurship great in Uzbekistan.

A mixed-methods approach will be used to understand the effectiveness of the innovation infrastructure in driving economic growth in Uzbekistan. This design integrates qualitative insights from stakeholders and quantitative data on economic and innovation performance. It aims to capture the nuanced realities of the innovation ecosystem while leveraging robust data analysis for comprehensive insights.

Conduct semi-structured interviews with a diverse set of stakeholders in the Uzbek innovation system. These stakeholders may include policymakers, industry leaders, researchers, entrepreneurs, and representatives from academic institutions.

Business skills can be learned. Individual key factors that determine the (lack of) success of female entrepreneurship are role models, family support, self-confidence and skills. Key professional development highlights that were mentioned often by surveyed business women are (in no particular order):

- Training in languages (Russian, English) and computer literacy should be targeted and delivered;
- Training opportunities in finance, accounting and taxes, business management, risk analysis and cost-benefit analysis should be targeted and delivered;
- Legal rights of entrepreneurs and responsibilities should be enforced and informed;

- Successful women role models, business mentors are in short supply.

Women also assess their role as female entrepreneurs very critically because of their (less) time devoted to their families as a spouse and a mother. Female entrepreneurs are in urgent need of basic educational training in entrepreneurship, languages (Russian, English), Uzbek labor code and regulations, accounting, marketing, human resources, IT services, business management and economics. Most Master classes should be organized with more experienced entrepreneurs (experts) by each sector with 'best practices'. Most women also find it hard to find role models, support networks and qualified specialists to expand their business. Telegram groups are helping women with networking and learning because women feel that there is large information vacuum to learn more about professional development opportunities and access to business networking events.

RESULTS

Uzbek women entrepreneurs are a relatively untapped economic resource. Our policy objective is to foster high-growth and high-quality entrepreneurship and receive high returns to entrepreneurship. The key questions for policy design to achieve this policy objective should be the following: how entrepreneurship occurs (self-employment, new firm formation), why it is undertaken (out of necessity or opportunity), and what activity or outcome it can yield (growth in sales or employment). Such measures are important to understand the dynamics of entrepreneurship types and outcomes. Based on our evidence from Uzbekistan, we conclude that female entrepreneurship mainly occurs as self-employment and it is undertaken out of necessity and it does not yield growth. These pieces of evidence suggest that policymakers have a huge opportunity to implement policies and provide institutional support to promote and make women entrepreneurship great in Uzbekistan.

Purposive sampling to ensure representation from key sectors and roles within the innovation ecosystem.

Review data from government and international organizations to understand macroeconomic trends, industry-specific performance, and foreign direct investment flows in Uzbekistan.

These typically repeat and weave together rather than always occur in chronological order. The steps involved in the social innovation process include identifying and analyzing societal challenges, enlisting the support of actors and resources, developing and testing new solutions, putting those solutions into practice and scaling them up, and demonstrating the value of the new solutions to individuals, organizations, and societal structures (Mulgan & Pulford, 2010; Lindberg, 2021; Westley et al., 2017). A micro level is where individual initiatives for social change are dealt with, a meso level is where these initiatives are organized, and a macro level is where the societal structures that both influence and are influenced by the initiatives are dealt with. The many roles and participants in the ecosystem

must support and facilitate all phases and stages of the process for social innovation to be able to contribute to long-lasting social change (Mulgan & Pulford, 2010; Lindberg, 2021.)

DISCUSSION

The Constitution of Uzbekistan guarantees all citizens the right to education. Young girls and women have no legal impediments or barriers to accessing any level of the educational system, which begins with pres-school and includes

mandatory primary and secondary general and special education. The higher education (tertiary-level) system includes institutions that implement academic and professional programs according to state standards. Gender balance in student enrollment varies by subsector but is preserved in primary and secondary general education. In professional colleges, the sex ratio of students has had near gender parity since 2009. However, gender disparities in higher education are still significant. In 2017, several higher educational institutions relaunched diverse correspondence courses that permit remote access, except for examinations. The renewal of correspondence studies has good potential for achieving gender balance in higher education.

From the point of view of ensuring gender equality, it is worth noting positive changes in education. In particular, since 2017, most universities opened part time departments in various specialties. This form of education empowers young women to care for children and fulfill other family obligations.

Taking this opportunity, I find it sensible to quote from the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the twentieth plenary meeting of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis on June 21, 2019:

“I am anxious about the stereotype that is rooted in the minds of our people. Normally, we revere a woman, primarily as a mother, the guardian of the family hearth. This is certainly true. However, today every woman should not be a passive bystander, but an active and proactive participant in the ongoing democratic transformations in the country.”

That day, by the proposal of the President, for the first time in the history of the country a woman Tanzila Narbaeva was elected the new Chair of the Senate. As you know, Tanzila Narbaeva held the post of Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chaired the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan.

Mentioning legislative action taken in this area, in September 2019, the Laws ‘On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for women and men’ and ‘On protecting women from harassment and violence’ were adopted in Uzbekistan in order to further improve the legal framework for ensuring and protecting women’s rights.

Almost all UN agencies, including the United Nations Development Program, the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the International Organization for Migration made comments and proposals on the two abovementioned laws.

Social norms in Uzbekistan, as in much of Central Asia, often emphasize traditional roles for women, which can restrict their mobility and career choices. However, there is a growing recognition of the need to shift these perceptions to harness the full potential of women in the economy. For example, following elections in December 2019, women's representation in the national parliament (Oliy Majlis) doubled from 16 per cent to 32 per cent - the highest in Central Asian region and above the global average of 24 per cent. However, only 2.9 per cent ministerial positions are held by women and all posts of hokims (governors) in 14 regions and Tashkent are held by men¹¹⁸. Furthermore, only 12 per cent of judges are women, and women in public administration are more likely to work in nondecision-making positions.

The institutional mechanisms for enforcement of the legal rights are:

The Women's
Committee of
Uzbekistan

Commission on Gender
Equality of the Republic
of Uzbekistan
(established in 2019)

Committee of Senate on
Women and Gender
Issues

Commission on Women
and Family Issues under
the Legislative Chamber

In 2021, Uzbekistan approved the Strategy for achieving Gender Equality until 2030, with a concrete program aimed at increasing women's participation in all spheres of political, economic, and social life. Efforts have led to an increase in the number of women pursuing higher education, with 50 percent of university students being women compared to 37 percent five years ago. The government has also prioritized supporting women's entrepreneurship.

CONCLUSION

In recommendation we would Develop specific scholarship programs and targeted recruitment initiatives aimed at increasing female enrollment in STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) fields. For this, we are must build a pipeline of female professionals equipped to lead and innovate in the key sectors that drive economic growth; create tailored financial products and services for women, including microfinance, grants, and venture capital dedicated to women-led startups. It can be to reduce the financial barriers that disproportionately affect women entrepreneurs and facilitate their active participation in the economy; Establish more platforms and forums that connect women with industry leaders and mentors, both domestically and internationally; Introduce more flexible work policies, maternity and paternity leaves, and quality childcare services at workplaces; Enforce quotas for female participation in decision-making roles both in public and private sectors.

Uzbekistan has made notable strides in improving gender equality through targeted policies and initiatives aimed at enhancing the educational and professional opportunities available to women. Key strategies such as the 'Women in Development' strategy and the state program on enhancing the role of women in society (2021-2025) have laid a strong foundation for supporting women's economic independence and their participation in public administration. Despite these advancements, there remains a significant need to further integrate women into innovation and high-leadership roles within the economy. The full engagement of women in these areas is essential not only for achieving gender parity but also for driving robust economic growth and sustainable development in Uzbekistan.

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